

English Literature as a Catalyst for Soft Skills Development in Higher Education

Tanveer Gulab¹ & Dr. L.V. Padmarani Rao²

¹Research Scholar, PG Department of English & Research Centre, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded.

²Research Supervisor, Professor and Head, PG Department of English & Research Centre, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya, Nanded.

Corresponding Author - Tanveer Gulab

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18775868

Abstract:

In the light of National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, educational reforms, reflective learning and use of ICT in the educational field shows the relevance of soft skills education in higher studies. In the contemporary educational context, the development of soft skills has become essential for the holistic learning of students and their professional growth. Thus this paper emphasizes soft skills as an integral part of learning through literature. As literature plays a significant role, it provides deeper insights into and understanding of human emotions and feelings. It functions as a laboratory and a pedagogical tool for soft skills development.

Thus this paper aims to conceptualize literature as a catalyst to accelerate and stimulates soft skills development. The literature organically helps to develop soft skills through reading, understanding and nurturing those skills via acceptance and not merely instructing and training individuals. Thus the key soft skills such as communication skills, emotional intelligence, empathy, critical thinking, decision-making, team-work culture and stress management can be developed efficiently in higher education. The market and nation require skilled workforce for the individual, societal and national growth. Hence literature can efficiently develop soft skills using analytical, critical and textual approaches to demonstrate the qualitative perspectives of literature in developing soft skills.

In higher education, India's potential human resource and productive demographic dividend can be built and nurtured fruitfully. Hence for undergraduates and postgraduates learners with teacher-students interaction in advanced learning environment soft skills development plays significant role. It also aligns with NEP 2020, which extensively focuses on skills-based education, employability and holistic development goals. Hence it is convenient to consider that literature functions as a powerful medium that actively promotes and enhances soft skills among young learners in higher education.

Keywords: *Soft Skills, NEP 2020, Higher Education, Communication Skills, ICT in Education, Undergraduates and Postgraduates Learners.*

Introduction:

Language is the landmark discovery in the human history where human has used speech to communicate and interact efficiently and with time oral sagas and written artistic records by ancient masters made prosperous human history. All these made significant impact on human mind. The development in the use of language has

made significant impact. English language has worldwide audience from very remote areas to completely connected digital world. English language has made a huge impact on the literature of the world.

In India during the colonization process English became the language of mainstream of education. The colonial policies have promoted

the western educational philosophy through English language. As a result of that English became the powerful language in India and connected itself smoothly towards the grounded realities of Indian society. After decolonization the regional and national voices emerged as a powerful tools to raise distress, harsh reality of the society, pain and sufferings as well. With time Indian English literature has also emerged with vibrant and powerful structures. Hence the language 'English' as a regional voice or thread of global connectivity has become the powerful tool in the form of literature.

English also became the voice of globe with its significant contribution in the form of literature such as American literature, African literature, Caribbean literature and Indian English literature as well. And the language of a one particular continent became the language of the global connectivity as it was also the by-product of tribe's speech. As it is said that 'literature is the criticism of life' hence human life has been best represented in the literature. Thus literature works as a catalyst and a laboratory for soft skills development.

Literature provides the deep insights and meaning to the life in the form of literature. Hence the literature is the foundational ground to nurture the values, develop emotions and human understanding through the characters. Soft skills improve human behavior and personality soft skills such as communication skills, emotional intelligence, critical thinking, decision-making, problem solving etc. Hence to develop the soft skills the catalyst role of literature is crucial.

Literature has provided the ground reality of the life in the form of artistic literary pieces. Hence the deeper understanding of literature will enhance the core learning ability of the learner w.r.t. soft skills.

Literature Review:

Historically, literature has marched successfully by entertaining people, communicating through characters, developing values and emotional connections among the people. Since the beginning of human history the prior focus was given on the development of hard skills. And hard skills were considered as the measurable competencies of human mind as crucial skills. Hence soft skills and its role somehow blurred under the curtain of hard skills. Whitmore (1972) discusses soft skills as non-technical capabilities that facilitate effective human interaction and adaptation. This has led to scholarly establishment of soft skills in educational field as the non-technical aspects. But it has lagged to establish literature as a powerful catalyst to integrate soft skills in real life learning.

Further the role of soft skills in higher education considered as the employability and curriculum design as Cimatti (2016) synthesized studies showing that higher education institutions needed to integrate soft skills into curricula to improve performance of learners and employability outcomes. Later Sen (2023) emphasized that literature provides a reflective space where students negotiate meaning and ambiguity, where Sen (2023) has theoretically tried to establish literature as a ground to develop soft skills.

As the education system shifted towards skills-based frameworks with the integration of NEP 2020 the empirical research grew. As a result of that to understand the classroom-based studies in higher education Wangmanee (2024) has conducted qualitative research using Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) with children's literature to understand English proficiency and soft skills among undergraduate students. Through story-based discussions, teamwork and group presentation activities students teamwork skills, creativity and critical

analysis increased. Further Korn and Rao (2024) examined the impact of instructional literature resources such as anthologies etc., on soft skills across diverse students groups related to technical and management. Aziz (2025) conducted a systematic review of soft skills development methods across higher education.

However these scholarly researches have greatly contributed in the understanding of the role of literature in soft skills development. The research has also asserted the significance of soft skills in employability and professional growth but the striking research gap was found in establishing literature as a laboratory and catalyst in developing soft skills. Hence this research paper conceptualizes the literature as a powerful tool and source to develop soft skills efficiently and with positive change in the performance.

Soft Skills in Higher Education:

Skill is the ability of a human to learn something. On the other hand the word *soft* in the context of soft skills education focuses on the part of human behavior. Hence soft skills are related to human behavior, they are the personal abilities of the individual to perform better in the life. Soft skills are essential aspects of human behavior. These skills enhance the behavior, performance and professional outcomes of the learners.

In higher education the focus was mainly on understanding the skills to be eligible to get the job or learn skills. These skills were

considered as a separate performance increasing abilities and tools. Hence proper attention has to pay on literature as a catalyst tool for soft skills development. Their proper understanding, importance and role is crucial to understand soft skills and the relation of literature.

1. Soft Skills vs. Hard Skills:

Soft skills are the basic personality traits and abilities of an individual to perform well in the life or in any situation. Soft skills are the part of life skills. These skills are more than dozens to count. Among them some of the most essential soft skills are leadership skills, confidence management, critical thinking, decision-making, communication skills, personality development skills, teamwork and emotional intelligence skills. These skills are non-technical in nature. These skills help to understand human behavior well in order to understand the society.

On the other hand hard skills are technical in nature, they are job specific, task specific. There are many hard skills according to the profession and work environment. Some of the important hard skills are Programming and software development, Graphic design, Carpentry, Artificial Intelligence, Foreign Languages and Statistical analysis etc. These hard skills make individual to be a job ready person and helps them to handle the work situation well. The key difference between them can be understood in the following way

Hard Skills	Soft Skills
Job specific	Individual development specific
Technical in nature	Non-technical in nature
Area and work specific acceptability	Wider area and acceptability
Focus on training in hand	Focus on practice with experience
Narrow scope	Wider scope
Performance oriented	Personality oriented
Examples include Graphic designs, Data operator etc.	Examples include communication skills, emotional intelligence

Fig.1: Difference between Soft Skills and Hard Skills

Thus it is soft skills are the composite part of skills based education, as its understanding can mold the character and their performance. And the proper distinction between hard skills and soft skills lead to better outcomes in the domain of higher education.

2. Role of Soft Skills in Higher Education:

Soft skills are crucial aspects of human personality. Soft skills have wider role to play. Under the process of colonization in India, due to the great influence of western education soft skills were taught as separately. Despite the ancient Indian education system focuses on soft skills as the integral part of human personality hence cannot be treated as separate entities to learn. After the globalization, the world became the 'global village' and choices made available for consumers across the globe. This service-driven world led the nations to focus on empowering the workforce at early educational level for better outcomes.

Hence the development of soft skills was among the learners were also became the need of educational setups. Even the National Education Policy 2020 focuses on skill-based education. Hence the role of soft skills such as empathy, critical thinking, decision-making, communication skills, and emotional intelligence etc. became crucial to understand. The role of soft skills in higher education can be understood in the following ways

- Soft skills are the basic abilities to transform the personality of the individual hence its proper understanding leads to desirable results and expected outcomes as well.
- These skills make learners more focused in understanding the situation well.
- Soft skills provide the ground level understanding of human behavior hence value-education can be inculcated.
- Students will develop empathy and emotional understanding about others.
- Shift in the role of students from merely a passive listener to active listener and speaker.
- Understanding of essential employability skills at early stage improves their performance.
- Soft skills will build critical thinking and decision-making hence learners' personality development will occur and learners become independent.
- Confidence management and behavioral awareness will occur.
- Potential resources will turn into productive resources hence the chances of employability will increases.
- These skills will aspire to achieve national education policy goals which focus on skill-based education.
- These skills will help in holistic learning.

Thus the role of soft skills is wider and comprehensive. It is essential to understand that the role of soft skills in education will bring transformation in the performance of the students.

English Literature and Soft Skills in Higher Education:

English literature has the wider audience, diversity and sagas of regions. English as a language of literature has contributed widely and enhanced the global diversity. Thus the role of English is merely not restricted to language only but instead it became the language of marginalized, the language of community, individual expressions and society.

Hence this language is become as the language of emotions, expressions and feelings. This language has become the language of behavioral change and performance growth. As

literature presents this human part of inner behavior hence the learning and understanding of soft skills through literature can widely contribute in higher education.

1. English Literature in Higher Education:

Literature is the criticism of life. Literature can be oral or written. It can be fictional or non-fictional, where the earlier is about imaginative life like novels, stories etc., and the latter is about real life such as autobiographies etc. It can be written in various genres such as novels, poetry, drama, short stories and essays etc. It includes canonical and contemporary literary texts also. It asserts the embedded themes such as cultural, social, ethical and psychological, which variously present the life. In higher education English literature functions and accelerates itself

- As an interpretative discipline
- A reflective space for exploring human experiences and values
- Asserts itself as a hub of values
- Becomes a medium for critical inquiry
- It functions in all multidisciplinary frameworks

Thus literature as a cultural classroom depicts the reality of life and imaginary world also. It has the ability to understand the real meaning of life. Hence English literature as a catalyst has to be understood to derive its real essence as well.

2. English literature as catalyst:

English literature as catalyst functions and signifies:

- As it implies acceleration in learning and not direct instruction
- It stimulates soft skills with essential emotional aspects and does not teach mechanically or technically
- It suggests an indirect but essentially powerful influence

- It makes teaching more insightful and understanding driven.

Hence all these possess literature in higher education as

- An experiential learning tool rather a static book
- An influential wave for personal and interpersonal growth
- A transformative academic practice
- A multidisciplinary field of study
- An engaging field of learning

Thus English literature as catalyst in higher education has much to do such as enlightening the brains, making the life of students meaningful by providing deeper insights, letting understand the sudden and motivation driven responses for better learning outcomes throughout the life.

English Literature and Soft Skills Development:

As the skills are learned and trained abilities of the individuals. Hence its proper understanding leads to enhance the development of human behavior and personality. Soft skills on the other hand are the personal qualities and essential characteristics of the individuals. They are non-technical in nature. These skills can be best understood in social life where human behavior, human culture and expected values intersect.

Hence the deeper understanding of literature influences the essential characteristics of human behavior. Soft skills such as emotional intelligence, critical thinking, empathy, decision-making, communication skills, personality development, and stress management etc. can be developed under the roof of English literature which can be understood in the following ways

Soft Skills Development	English Literature	Role in Higher Education
Communication Skills	Can be developed through the characters understanding in literary text, their interaction with others in the literature such as in <i>Pride and Prejudice</i> (1813) by Jane Austen depicts this through Elizabeth's character	Enhances visibility and boosts memory retention of students which help to reflective level
Emotional Intelligence	Understood via how characters in different situations control over their emotions or not; how they respond to sudden situations such as it was shown in <i>My Financial Career</i> (1910) by Stephen Leacock through the character of the narrator	Let them to understand emotions are not weakness of anyone but their understanding and control over them matter. These will lead to better handling of the situation in real life
Stress Management	In stressful situation and past trauma also human values and dignity is crucial to understand the sufferings of others is asserted in <i>Final Solutions</i> by Mahesh Dattani	Crucial for learners handle the stress as a skill and not as weakness and emotional degradation
Personality Development and Empathy	It can be understood via how characters help each other and the real impact on their lives. How small actions can also bring positive changes. This can be understood through the short story's characters Olga and Sergei in the <i>The Beggar</i> (1887) by Anton Chekhov	Essential values of helping others and later help in developing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). It also makes learner to empathize with people and understand their situation. In future it will discourage corrupt practices
Leadership Skills	Understood and developed through how characters take decisions in their lives; how they tackle real life situation. In the poem the traveler chooses the path which was less-discovered as narrated in <i>The Road Not Taken</i> by Robert Frost	It helps learners take their own decisions in the life. It provides them with moral support and deeper understanding
Teamwork and Decision-Making	In difficulties helping each-others, considering human values at peak rather than past biases and working for common cause as shown in <i>Final Solutions</i> by Mahesh Dattani through Ramnik and Smita's characters	Helpful for students personal and professional growth

Fig.2: Soft Skills Development through English Literature in Higher Education

This figure 2, shows how soft skills can be developed through literature and how they are helpful in higher education. The role of soft skills is wider and concrete in educational field

especially for professional growth. The expected outcomes can be stated as in the following way

- Soft skills development through English literature in higher education will enhance thoughtful engagement of learners

- It will lead to better understanding of the characters and their role hence can impact in real life of the learners
- It leads to expand visual imaginative memory which will guide learners as a moral force in real life
- It helps the learners to understand real life based issues more deeply through literary analysis of the characters in the literature
- It will lead to enhance core aspects of language learning skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing (LSRW skills)
- It helps in holistic development of students and enhance learning outcomes
- It helps in personality development of the learners or humans and hence their professional growth
- Enhances employability outcomes and growth prospectives
- It nurtures value-based education as integral part of character development and hence the promotion of Eastern philosophy
- It will lead to strong foundation in higher education for holistic learning and growth.

Thus the role of soft skills through English literature has wider role in holistic development. It has also a great contribution in higher education. Hence the language and literature can bring more positive outcomes and enhance learner centric growth. Thus the understanding of soft skills and its development through literature is crucial for holistic development of the learners. As the holistic development of an individual can happen in the group or society and not in the isolation as Aristotle has rightly said, ‘man is a social animal’.

References:

- [1] Austen, J. (2003). *Pride and prejudice* (V. Jones, Ed.). Penguin Classics. (Original work published 1813).
- [2] Aziz, S. (2025). Soft skills development methods in higher education: A systematic literature review. *Higher Education Skills and Work-based Learning*, 15(4). (Publisher platform — ScienceDirect)
- [3] Chekhov, A. (2020). *The Beggar* (C. Garnett, Trans.). SAGA Egmont. (Original work published 1887)
- [4] Dattani, M. (2000). Final solutions. In *Collected plays* (pp. 165–230). Penguin Books India.
- [5] Frost, R. (1916). The road not taken. In *Mountain interval* (pp. 19–20). Henry Holt and Company.
- [6] Gulab, T., & Padmarani Rao, L. V. (2025). Stress Management Skills as a Soft Skill in Mahesh Dattani’s Play Final Solutions. *Research Journal of English (RJOE)*, 10(4), 592–602. <https://doi.org/10.36993/RJOE.2025.10.4.602>.
- [7] Gulab, T., & Rao, L. V. P. (2025). The role of soft skills in literature: Addressing challenges of the 21st century. *International Journal of English and Studies (IJOES)*, 7(12), 355–363. <https://doi.org/10.47311/IJOES.2025.7.12.363>.
- [8] Korn, B., & Rao, K. N. (2024). Enhancing soft skills through literature: Exploring the impact of instructional resources. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 12(1).
- [9] Leacock, S. (2010). My financial career. In *Literary Lapses* (pp. 13-16). McClelland & Stewart. (Original work published 1910).
- [10] Sen, D. (2023). Exploring the integration of English literature in soft skills training. *Journal of Research in English Studies (JRSpELT)*.
- [11] Wangmanee, P. (2024). Enhancing English and soft skills through CLIL and children’s literature: A qualitative case study. *Journal of Studies in the English Language*, 19(2), 1–25.